

Proceedings

Analyzing historical trends in trip generation by primary modes of transport in the Metropolitan Region of São Paulo between 1967 and 2017

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Abstract: This study analyzes the trip generation by main modes of transport and their trends over time in the Metropolitan Region of São Paulo (MRSP). Results point to a gradual growth for all modes of transport, except taxis. Moreover, the RM showed a higher growth in trip generation, employment, and population than SP. Individual modes of transport had a more expressive growth than collective ones. Regarding the share of all modes of transport, the RM had an increase while SP showed a reduction. The increase in trip generation has kept pace with population and employment growth, especially in the RM.

Keywords: OD Research; Transportation planning; MRSP.

Citation: Daroncho C. et al. Analyzing historical trends in trip generation by primary modes of transport in the Metropolitan Region of São Paulo between 1967 and 2017. *SUPTM 2024 conference proceedings* sciforum-082557. <https://doi.org/10.31428/10317/13578>

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1. Introduction

São Paulo underwent a rapid process of urbanization and industrialization from the late 19th century that completely reorganized its space utilization [1], turning the São Paulo capital into the main Brazilian industrial hub. The region's population growth also increased considerably, reaching its first million inhabitants in 1928 [2]. However, that the urban planning developed for São Paulo at the time failed to keep pace with this population growth and urban sprawl itself, resulting in several issues for transport [3].

At a national level, Brazil's process of urbanization and modernization in recent decades saw changes in the social reproduction and consumption needs of a large part of the population, especially the middle class. This segment expanded quantitatively and underwent a profound change in their lifestyle [4].

In this scenario of expanding activities and increasing distances, motorized modes of transport and economic resources to pay the costs involved became necessary. Consequently, given the transformations in urban space, the poor conditions of public transportation systems, and the good circulation and parking conditions, the automobile gained economic and sociological importance, becoming an indispensable instrument for its reproduction as a class [4].

Hence, this study seeks mainly to describe the phenomenon of trip generation by the main modes of transport and their respective share and trends developed in time and space. For this purpose, we analyzed the trip generation by main modes of transport between the years of the Origin-Destination survey conducted by the São Paulo Metropolitan Company, which began in 1967 and has been repeated every ten years.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study area

This study used the territorial scope referring to the Metropolitan Region of São Paulo – MRSP (Figure 1), which occupies an area of 7,946.96 km² and comprises 39 cities – 38 municipalities and the city of São Paulo. MRSP has a population of 21 million inhabitants (2,714.41 inhabitants/km²), corresponding to 47.54% of the population of the state of São Paulo [5].

Figure 1. MRSP and OD Zones of the São Paulo Metropolitan Company survey [6]

2.1. Data analysis

Data were collected from the São Paulo Metropolitan Company's Origin-Destination survey carried out in 1977, 1987, 1997, 2007, and 2017. Our main variable was "trip generation" by main modes of transport, namely: bus, charter, school bus, car (driver), car (passenger), taxi, minibus, subway, train, motorcycle, bicycle, walking, others. We defined two distinct regions for analysis: the city of São Paulo (SP) and the other 38 municipalities that make up the Metropolitan Region (RM).

Hence, we calculated the individual shares of each mode of transport regarding total trip generation in the MRSP, and for São Paulo (SP) and the RM separately. We also calculated the variations in trip generation by main modes of transportation in each subsequent year of the survey and the reference year (1977) for the MRSP, São Paulo, and the Metropolitan Region.

Collective and individual motorized trips were then calculated similarly. Collective trips encompass the following modes of transport: bus, charter, school bus, subway, and train. Individual trips consist of the following modes of transport: car (driver), car (passenger), taxi, and motorcycle. As "walking" and "bicycle" are considered non-motorized modes of transport, they were excluded from this last analysis.

Finally, trip generation and variations for each survey year were calculated in total terms (without distinction by mode of transport) in the MRSP, as well as the number of jobs and population and their respective variations. "OD homogenous zones" are defined based on their urban and socioeconomic homogeneity: compatibility with the limits of municipalities and districts in the city of São Paulo; compatibility with the limits of census tracts of the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE); homogeneity in the use and occupation of urban space; existing and future transportation system, urban equipment; physical barriers and empty areas [12].

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows transport modes (bus, charter, subway, train, car – driver, car – passenger, taxi, motorcycle, bicycle and walking) shares in total trip generation and variation in SP and the RM per survey year, having 1977 as the reference year. It is possible to

observe that in all modes of transport there was an increase in the participation of RM and a decrease in the participation of SP.

Figure 2. Transport modes shares in total trip generation and variation (ref 1977) per survey year [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]

All modes of transport grew (compared to 1977), except for chartered transport (-22.6% in RM and -81.7% in SP), buses (-9.6% in SP) and taxis (-26.6% in SP). In general terms, RM achieved greater percentage increases compared to SP. Still, the biggest increases were Motorcycle, mainly in RM (+9721.3%). Taxi mode experienced a drastic decrease in trip production in 1987, 1997 and 2007, however, it saw a considerable increase in 2017.

4. Conclusion

Regarding the modes of transport analyzed, in terms of variation per survey year, buses, cars, subway, train, motorcycle, walking, and bicycle showed a gradual increase over the 50 years, highlighting a consolidation scenario for these modes of transport.

Conversely, chartered transport has shown a gradual decrease over the past decades, indicating the disuse of this mode of transport over time. This is also the case for the trolleybus, which accounted for the total trip generation of this type of mass transport only in 1977. In the 1987 survey, this mode of transport already shared trip generation with diesel buses. By 1997, there were no more records on trolleybus trip generation, as this mode of transport became obsolete against the new technology.

We considered trip generation from conventional taxis only until 2007, and from 2017 onwards, ride-hailing applications were included in the sum—before 2017, such technology did not exist. Thus, we observed an intense negative variation between 1977 and 1987, and then an intense positive variation between 2007 and 2017.

This first finding may be explained by the high variation in taxi fares in the decades from 1980 to 2000, the regulation and control to which taxis were subjected, as well as the monopoly that came to exist. The positive variation, seen since the 2010s, stems from the emergence of ride-hailing applications (Uber, Cabify, 99, Easy Taxi, BlaBlaCar, etc.), generating greater competition among service providers and cheaper fares.

The high growth of motorcycle mode shows that this mode of individual transport has become an important option for transport in the metropolis, especially in the RM, where the average family income is lower.

This section is not mandatory but may be added to summarize results of the research presented at the conference. This research received no external funding, and the authors declare no conflict of interest.

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